

945358-BIGPICTURE
Central Repository for Digital Pathology

WP2 - Infrastructure and database hosting

D2.08 - Report on status of operational services implementation

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Document History

Version	Date	Description
V0.1	29 May 2023	For PMO review
V0.2	7 Jun 2023	For MB review
V1.0	19 Jun 2023	For PMO execution of submission; minor corrections possible
V1.1	28 Jun 2023	Final version for submission

Abstract

This report provides a description of the state of the operational system at the time when the first real non-clinical data submissions are being prepared and submitted. The system was established and operational M10, and has since been iteratively improved by wp2, based on needs identified by the rest of the project (wp3-6) according to project priorities (wp1) within available time and resources (wp2).

This is a follow-up to a similar report made during T2.5 - Pilot operation (D2.04 - Report on status of operational services implementation, M18) for the purpose of describing findings from this iterative improvement work. Despite being originally intended for supporting genetics research specifically, the ELIXIR technologies that the Bigpicture repository infrastructure is building upon have proven to be quite generically capable, and have been met with uniformly positive feedback from the digital pathology users of the Bigpicture repository services during the first years of the project. In fact, only very little in terms of negative feedback or even feature development requests have arisen.

From this, we conclude that the platform is highly suited to meet needs in digital pathology, at least among those highly technologically advanced users that have pioneered use of the Bigpicture repository infrastructure services (DECI, MUW, RUMC, RÖ, UMCU). However, as the project moves to more advanced usage patterns and opens up to broader ranges of user organisation which may not have access to the same degree of technological expertise as have our pioneers, we do anticipate that the needs for feature development could rise, for example implementing further usability features for less tech-savvy users.

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Methods

This section describes the process under which the results were produced. The results themselves are preferentially described in the [Results](#) section.

The system was operational M10, as reported in D2.2 - Report on the pilot system establishment, and has been iteratively improved ever since, in tasks T2.6 - Iterative development and T2.7 - Regular security review, both of which will be ongoing throughout the remainder of the project. Iterative improvement has been carried out as per the Description of the Action (DoA), meaning the platform services originally developed by ELIXIR for facilitating genetics research are operated and continuously adapted to needs in digital pathology research, based on feature requests from the rest of the project (wp3-6, data contribution and use, legal and sustainability aspects) according to project priorities (wp1) and within available time and resources (wp2). The status of the system was previously reported during T2.5 - Pilot operation (D2.04 - Report on status of operational services implementation, M18). The purpose of this report is to describe findings from iterative improvement work in the intervening period.

Organisation and work methodology

The Scrum based work methodology described in D2.04 is still in use. The products that support Bigpicture repository services are developed and operated by several scrum teams. Decision making is open and transparent and preferably pushed as close to active operations as possible, as is access to information. All wp2 meetings are open to attendance by any project partner. Overarching decisions are made in weekly wp2 management meetings with work package leadership, where service operating product owner representatives participate. Other venues have been set up for technical discussions, including weekly online meetings among the product owners and the work package lead; every other week with all developers invited. Since the sensitive data service area has grown steadily in the last decade, the teams operating and developing these services have expanded and reorganised several times in this period. To facilitate collaborative work among the growing distributed teams, multiple physical meetings between the wp2 development teams have been arranged in this period, including a Dec 2022 wp2 developer workshop and a May 2023 CSC-NBIS workshop in Helsinki. WP2 representatives also attended at a broader secure infrastructure workshop in Tarttu May 2023, aimed at coordinating and aligning efforts that use the same underlying services and standards, with representation from Bigpicture, FEGA, GDI, EUCAIM, 1+MG, B1MG, and a host of other Nordic national services.

Requirement dialogue

Successful development of complex systems such as the Bigpicture platform requires effective information and knowledge exchange, to adequately inform decision making at appropriate levels. Decision making regarding wp2 iterative service development takes place at service level, reference group level, work package level, and managing board level, as appropriate, as described below. Cross-work-package information and knowledge exchange takes place in topical meetings and in task forces, as described below.

Decision making

Targets for iterative improvement are identified through several means. Some things such as bugs or minor inconveniences can be addressed by wp2 immediately upon notification by beneficiaries using the services, however larger changes to features or introduction of new functionality require decision making in other work packages, to ensure the changes are in line with requirements, commitments, and expectations that exist among other beneficiaries.

In all matters affecting content of contributed data, and means and purposes of processing thereof, the

data contributing beneficiaries as rights holders to the data under their own control remain the sole authorities for decision making. WP3 leadership identifies and communicates the consensus for what improvements are considered reasonable and acceptable to the contributors, while supported by wp5 guidance on ethical and regulatory matters. In cases where needs are identified by beneficiaries in other roles and work packages, such as needs identified by data users and frontend developers (wp4) for example for increased reusability or interoperability, or needs identified for supporting strong business cases for sustainability (wp6), then, these needs for improvement can be addressed by wp2 if supported by work package decision or the description of the action (DoA), with the caveat as per above that improvements that affect content of contributed data, or the means and purposes of processing thereof, must always be supported by wp3 decision to ensure alignment with data contributors. Requests for iterative improvement communicated to wp2 in this way are addressed by wp2 within available budget and resources, and according to project priorities. If at any point project priorities should be ambiguous, wp2 intends to seek advice from wp1 and PMO, or, if needed, escalate to the managing board for decision and disambiguation.

Reference group for discovery services

The Reference group for discovery services is an example of the decision making process outlined above.

To accelerate iterative development of data discoverability services, the managing board has instated a small reference group consisting of wp3 representatives, namely representatives of the data collector node coordinators and current data contributors. Since this reference group decides on matters affecting content of contributed data, and means and purposes of processing thereof, the managing board has composed the reference group of wp3 representatives exclusively. Service release decisions are made by the managing board.

As per the DoA, Bigpicture is currently developing two data discoverability services; the Bigpicture landing page website, and a discoverability search service based on Beacon technology. These services are public-facing systems for search and overview information on datasets, and are intended to provide easy-to-use interfaces to allow users to easily find data of interest on the platform, and guide users to apply for access to the data.

The operational prototype services are continuously developed by wp2, and the reference group meets weekly with wp2 developers to review improvements and decide on direction of development until the next meeting. In parallel, the data contributor representatives in the reference group make continual assessment of how well and readily their existing data contributions can be represented in each successive iteration. This allows the reference group to interactively map out reasonable designs for these services, in terms of what metadata parameters should be available to these services, and how they should be searched and displayed in order to provide an appropriate amount of information to convey relevance yet still not risking disclosure of any potentially confidential details. This work of course also helps inform wp3 metadata standards development, as it helps wp3 develop a better understanding of how metadata parameters should be defined - and how data should be collected and processed to populate these parameters - in order to enable building the kind of platform interfaces and content that Bigpicture needs.

The reference group for discovery services is working iteratively with wp2 developers to define further metadata parameters that should be available to these services, and how they should be searched and displayed in order to provide an appropriate amount of information to convey relevance yet still not risking disclosure of any potentially confidential details. Such decisions could concern how search results should be presented, in order to decrease risk of unintentional disclosure of confidential details through repeated queries. This work of course also helps inform wp3 metadata standards development, as it helps wp3 develop a better understanding of how metadata parameters should be defined - and how data should be collected and processed to populate these parameters - in order to enable building the kind of platform interfaces and content that Bigpicture needs.

Task forces

To facilitate discussion and identification of needs for development, the Bigpicture managing board has instated task forces that act on delegation from the managing board, to address topics of cross-work-package concern. Four of them are of special relevance to this report and are briefly described here:

The Architecture task force, hosted by wp2, consists of members of the managing board and other beneficiary representatives work to map out and develop the Bigpicture enterprise architecture.

The GDPR task force, hosted by wp5, which has coordinated cross-work-package information gathering to support the wp5 work to develop a legal framework for data sharing in the project. WP2 participates in the GDPR task force to provide the data processor service provider perspective.

The Honest Data Broker task force, hosted by wp3 has been developing the processes for data submission and data access granting. CSC is developing and hosting Resource Entitlement Management System (REMS) portal. The services accessing data need to integrate to REMS interfaces that the authenticated user gets the data access permissions from. The task force is currently working to develop a set of easily understandable terms of use for Bigpicture datasets.

The Metadata task force, hosted by wp3, addresses data standardisation and develops the Bigpicture metadata formats. WP2 was very active in the initiation of the metadata task force, for the purpose of getting discussion started; to provide expertise on the operation and data formats used by the baseline platform services, and to advise on least-friction ways of extending them to other disciplines in order not to necessitate a full service redesign nor causing interoperability issues with the baseline services, which remain in production to support research in genetics. For data repository administrative purposes, the administrative metadata regarding the organisation is essential. This is for example needed for data ownership and reporting. Successful metadata standardisation work remains of fundamental importance to Bigpicture, and arguably to the entire future of digital pathology, as it is key to safe collection and contribution of consistent and unambiguous data, which is the foundation upon which all other value in Bigpicture arises. The work in the task force remains intense, and has branched out to several sub-groups that cover various individual specialised aspects of metadata, such as metadata for directly accessible datasets, for AI models, and for information on data contributors. As CSC is developing the discovery service implementation, the requirements discussion is mostly about the metadata and also user interface and functionalities. WP3 decides the work prioritisation focusing on the selection of searched attributes. It is anticipated that once the metadata standard for directly accessible datasets have matured further, the metadata task force will take on standardisation of metadata for more advanced usage patterns, such as indirect access to datasets and AI algorithms.

At this moment in time an update of the legal framework, which covers contribution of personal data as well as information on platform users, is in progress. Once this is in place, we anticipate wp2 will be able to resume contributing its experiences from past metadata standardisation efforts to the Bigpicture efforts.

Results

The figures in the following section (Fig. 1-13) show graphical illustration of steps in the Bigpicture platform user story. These figures are taken from a concept presentation of a simple platform usage scenario that was originally presented for consideration by the managing board on 2022-10-21, and later used as basis for a practical hands-on demonstration using live operational services on 2023-01-30, in the opening plenary session of the Bigpicture annual meeting onsite in Vienna. Webcasts were also made of select service demonstrations, for the benefit of consortium members wanting to review the demonstrations, or who were unable to join this session. The webcasts are available to consortium members.

The services are described in individual sections below.

User authentication and authorisation

As per the DoA, Bigpicture will use the Life Science Login (“LS Login” in short) service of Life Science AAI (LS AA) to facilitate authentication and authorisation of user access to services and data as necessary. An overview description of this service is available in D2.02 - Report on the pilot system establishment. The transition/rebrand from ELIXIR AAI to Life Science AAI anticipated in the D2.02 report has since been carried out, uneventfully.

Bigpicture has decided to use the Life Science AAI and its group management system (Perun) to allow customer organisations to self-administer accounts and groups (Fig 1, 2). The services will use a mixture of account management, authentication and authorisation processes, described separately per service below, to enable pilot use for service development purposes.

The first step of the workflow, illustrated in Fig. 1, is that individual staff at organisations looking to use platform services obtain accounts at an identity provider that is trusted by Life Science AAI. Such identity providers can include the user's normal home organisation login, such as for most academic institutions in Europe which are connected to the eduGAIN identity trust federation, or popular internet service providers like ORCID, LinkedIn or Google. If for some reason a platform user organisation deems none of these identity providers are suitable for use, then they can decide to use the option to create a Life Science AAI Hostel identity provider for their use with Bigpicture platform services. In this manner Bigpicture does not need to operate identity provider services including user registration and user profile management.

In the next step, shown in Fig. 2, a platform user organisation uses Perun groupware to create groups authorised to act in their name, and add verified users to these groups. This is carried out by account managers appointed by the platform user organisation and entrusted with the responsibility to create and manage the organisation's Bigpicture groups, and to assign membership to users whose identities have been appropriately validated.

Fig. 3. Data user using Life Science AAI to log in to a platform service.

The Life Science AAI login procedure is designed to provide a least-surprises means of accessing platform services. The user experience is illustrated in Fig. 3. Here, our example data user is from an organisation that is trusted by Life Science AAI (in this case by extension, from Linköping University being part of the eduGAIN identity trust federation) meaning the user can just type a few characters into the search box and click to be transferred to their home organisation identity provider, to proceed with whatever login procedure is normal in their home organisation.

The platform user groups can be given authorised access to different platform services, as shown in Fig. 4. This is useful for enabling on-platform work in parallel, potentially using different datasets that for various reasons should not be combined. This can be useful for example to facilitate work by research groups that operate under different ethical approvals. Fig. 4 shows the SD Desktop service specifically, however the Bigpicture platform also provides further services, described in the sections below. [SD Desktop](#) is also described in a separate section below.

Data submission

The general process of data submission was previously described in D2.04 - Report on status of pilot services implementation.

As per the DoA, wp2 provides robust backend APIs to enable users to upload datasets to the platform. Frontend user interfaces for dataset submission integrating with these backend APIs are being developed by wp4, for example in the form of upcoming added functionalities in Cytomine. In the meantime, wp2 is providing the frontend tools that were developed for use with these backend services in the field of genetics research, in the form of a compact suite of open source Sensitive Data Archive Command Line Tools, `sda-cli`¹, previously described for example in D2.05 - Report on pilot operations. The intention is that users will eventually authenticate and be authorised to use the data submission APIs through the use of Life Science AAI and the Perun group based account management workflow described in the [User authentication and authorisation](#) section above, which will provide an automated mechanism to ensure that only users authorised to contribute datasets on behalf of their organisation will be able to do so. This is expected to become possible once the project adopts its upcoming legal framework for data sharing (cf GDPR task force; [Task forces](#) section above). Until such a time, to enable pilot use for service development purposes, the project uses an interim solution where data contributors communicate directly to the service operating beneficiaries written instruction detailing exactly which individuals (affiliation, name, email) are authorised to contribute datasets on their behalf.

¹ <https://github.com/NBISweden/sda-cli>

Before transmitting a dataset to the platform over the internet -even over an encrypted connection- data contributors must first encrypt the dataset with a Bigpicture repository service public key. This is to ensure that no one except the intended recipient data centre can read the contents of the transmitted files, even if the uploading user should transmit the files to the wrong destination by mistake. Fig. 5 illustrates how a user authorised to upload datasets on behalf of a data contributor organisation uses `sda-cli` to encrypt a dataset locally before uploading it to the platform. The dataset holds images and metadata, including terms of data use and information on whether the data is anonymized.

In order for the submission to be accepted by the repository, it must validate correctly against the Bigpicture metadata standard which is being developed by wp3 (cf Metadata task force, [Task forces](#) section above). Currently, standards are being developed for Mandatory Submission Metadata for Directly Accessible Datasets (MSM_{dad} , initially described in D3.02 Minimal dataset deliverable) and are expressed using XSD files. At the time of writing, MSM_{dad} v0.1.1 is used, and dataset validation is carried out through XSD validation. Dataset validation is expected to be carried out using the same tools before and after transfer, first by the data uploader to avoid wasting time on lengthy uploads of an incorrect dataset, and then by the platform to both to ensure that data was not corrupted in transfer, and to avoid ingestion of malicious or corrupted data.

In the time since the D2.04 - Report on status of pilot services implementation, data users and platform application service developers identified a need for standardising also folder structures inside datasets. This would lead to increased ease of use of data cross-datasets, as well as facilitated fast access to archive data for application services like Cytomine, which currently rely on folder structures to identify files that need quick serving in order not to slow down data visualisation and interaction. Such semantic extension to the metadata standards could necessitate more advanced dataset validation techniques than the current straightforward XSD based validation methodology. Metadata standards and validators, as well data extraction- and conversion tools, are developed and adopted by wp3 (optionally using input from data users in wp4), and wp2 performs platform side dataset validation using metadata standards versions. When the project adopts its upcoming legal framework for data sharing (cf GDPR task force; [Task forces](#) section above), wp2 will be able to contribute to validator development if

needed, within available resources and according to project priorities (cf the [Requirement dialogue](#) and [Decision making](#) sections above).

In the current data submission implementation, images and metadata are uploaded to the repository through the same backend interface, for example using the sda-cli frontend. Here, metadata submission consists of simply uploading the metadata files to a special subdirectory to the dataset submission directory named "metadata". On successful dataset validation, metadata is ingested from this location and stored separately from the image files.

WP2 is also developing a separate metadata submitter interface SD Submit (previously described in D2.02 Report on the pilot system establishment, D2.04 - Report on status of pilot services implementation, and D2.05 - Report on pilot operations). This interface will store the submitted metadata and validate against the schemes. It will check against the data files and create DOI when requested.

Datasets for indirect access only are expected to have radically different requirements in terms of metadata parameters and their status as mandatory or optional (cf Metadata task force; Task forces section above). The flexibility in dataset validation outlined here is expected to become useful as metadata standards mature and are updated to accommodate for new identified needs, for example arising from wp3 and wp4 work on demonstrators for indirect usage patterns.

The sda-cli command line interface was originally developed as a generic tool to simplify data submission to sensitive data archives. From Bigpicture data contributor feedback, we conclude that the sda-cli toolset is highly suited to meet needs in digital pathology, at least among those highly technologically advanced users that have pioneered use of the Bigpicture repository infrastructure services (DECI, MUW, RÖ, UMCU). However, as the project moves to enable more advanced usage patterns such as indirect access to datasets and AI algorithms, and opens up to broader ranges of user organisation which may not have access to the same degree of technological expertise as have our pioneers, we do anticipate that the needs for feature development could rise. WP2 will take on such development tasks as needs are identified, within available resources and according to project priorities (cf the [Requirement dialogue](#) and [Decision making](#) sections above).

Discovery services

As per the DoA, Bigpicture will enable data discovery functionality using at least four different services, for public internet search, for more detailed drill-down, for "mining your own data", and export integration with other research infrastructure information systems. Three of these are developed by wp2 and are described in the following sections; [Landing pages](#), [Discovery search service](#), and Discovery export. A third is developed by wp4 (Cytomine), and may build upon the wp2 services that are described here.

Landing pages

As per the DoA, wp2 is providing a website for dataset landing pages. A landing page is a fully public, Search Engine Optimised (SEO) web page with information about a dataset, providing an overview description of the dataset and how to get access to it. Every dataset will have a landing page, which is generated directly on dataset submission based on landing page specific fields in submission metadata. As per the DoA, Bigpicture will make the datasets more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) by assigning them DataCite Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) to make the datasets citable in scientific research publications, if so desired by the data contributor, and if necessary information for creating a DOI is provided by the contributor. The landing page for a dataset having a DOI will also serve as the DOI landing page for that dataset. Assigning DOIs to datasets also make the Bigpicture

repository and datasets more easily discoverable using FAIR services for OpenScience, such as DataCite's re3data.org.

According to wp3 decision, the Bigpicture landing page service are developed iteratively, with a starting point in a direct clone of an existing production service operated by a wp2 beneficiary, in this case the AIDA Data Hub landing page website² operated by LiU. This decision by wp3 mimics the development methodology used for all other repository infrastructure services development in Bigpicture. To accelerate development, the managing board has instated a small reference group consisting of data collector node coordinators and current data contributors to make decisions for rapid prototype development. The reference group is currently developing standards for landing page specific fields in submission metadata, in an iterative fashion, together with developers in wp2. The process and decision making employed in this work is described in the [Reference group for discovery services](#) section above. When approved, these standards will feed into the next version MSM_{dad} and be used in the collection of upcoming datasets.

Fig. 6. A data user uses a normal web browser to search for datasets of interest. AIDA is used in this example to demonstrate the effects of good search engine optimization in an established high quality production service. A dataset from the AIDA Data Hub is indeed presented as the top hit. Also, the example images provided on the landing page for this dataset have been picked up by the search engine, and given prominent presentation already in the search results.

² <https://datahub.aida.scilifelab.se/datasets/>

Data User

Skin data from the Visual Sweden project DROID
doi:10.23698/aida/drsk

AIDA Data Hub facilitating FAIR data sharing for medical imaging diagnostics

The dataset consists of 99 H&E-stained whole slide skin images (WSI) - 49 abnormal and 50 normal cases. All significant abnormal findings identified are outlined and categorized into 13 types such as actinic keratosis, basal cell carcinoma and dermatofibroma. Other tissue components, such as epidermis, adnexal structures, as well as the surgical margin are delineated to create a complete histological map. In total, 16741 separate annotations have been made to segment the different tissue structures and link them to ontological information.

Keywords: Pathology, Skin, Cancer, Whole slide imaging, Annotated

Sample images

Sample images with reduced image quality. Please click to preview.

Apply for Access

Dataset information

Fig. 7. Example landing page for a dataset shared through AIDA Data Hub.

The purpose of search engine optimising the landing pages is to make datasets easy to find in a normal internet search, which is illustrated in Fig. 6. This optimisation is done by providing the landing page information in two formats in parallel; one visually appealing and easily understandable to humans (cf example in Fig. 7), and a schema.org LD-JSON information package embedded in the html head, which is structured to be easily parsed by computers. This characterises semantic elements, such as example images, so as to make them more interlinkable and presentable in other services, such as the in the results view in normal internet searches.

The landing page itself holds basic information about the dataset, both as structured information and as free text. In the current setup, inherited from AIDA Data Hub, the information on the landing page is filled in entirely at the data contributor's discretion, however the reference group may decide that some fields should be made mandatory in the Bigpicture counterpart. The landing page also holds overview descriptions of terms of use and how to apply for access. In the Bigpicture landing page service, this is intended to be implemented as a button that takes the user to the access application form in REMS for the dataset, described in the [Entitlement management](#) section below.

Discovery search service

While search engine optimised landing pages provides broad and easy data discovery through normal internet searches (as described in the [Landing pages](#) section), Bigpicture also is also developing a custom discoverability service for detailed privacy-preserving queries, across federated repositories. As per the DoA, wp2 is developing this service based on Beacon Network technology. This was previously

described in D2.02 - Report on the pilot system establishment. For economy of scale, Bigpicture does not fund federated nodes, however wp2 runs one anyway, in small scale for testing and experimentation purposes, to ensure that the technology supports it and to ensure continued ease of deployment.

Fig. 8. A data user uses the Bigpicture discovery search service to search across federated nodes for datasets of interest.

As shown Fig. 8 above, four metadata fields have been defined as searchable by the data contributors. In the search results, datasets containing matching datasets will be presented along with links to more information and to apply for access. The intention is that this will be implemented as links to the dataset landing page and REMS application page, respectively, which are described in separate sections Landing pages and Entitlement management in this report.

The Bigpicture discovery search service is decided to be for registered use only. Thus, the users would need to authenticate first and they need to be part of the organisational groups. The landing pages would be the public source of information about the datasets.

Often, there is a trade-off between usability and privacy preservation, and the reference group must carefully consider how this balance can be appropriately struck. Both for the data that has been contributed already, but also so that planned collection of future datasets can be carried out safely and effectively while keeping this use in mind. Such considerations could include whether the service should display exact number of matching images per dataset, or whether such numbers should instead

be stratified and approximated (e.g. 10, 20, 50, 100, 200, 500, ...), or whether datasets with fewer than a certain number of matching images should even be reported in the search results. It is expected that the discovery search service will be used predominantly by AI researchers in search of large volumes of data for use in AI training, who will reasonably be more interested in going through an access request process for datasets having larger numbers of images in them that match their search queries. This could allow Bigpicture more leeway in prioritising privacy preservation over usability, as the risks of privacy breach increase with low numbers and higher precision, neither of which may be high interest factors to an AI research user.

There are ideas to enable "mine your own data" functionality for data which User has got granted access. One feature could be to create an exportable list of the matching image IDs.

For federated queries, the reference group may decide to limit responses from federated nodes to report not the number of matching images per dataset, but only the number of datasets that contain matching images, or even just a Boolean yes/no response to confirm whether or not the federated node has any matching images at all. If so, a positive response should be accompanied by a link that allows the user to repeat the query directly at the federated node, to reveal the details that were not provided through the federated search interface at the central repository. These measures are being considered because one of the reasons an organisation might want to operate their own Bigpicture federated node is that the data held in that federated node might not be legally permitted to move to other jurisdictions be it in whole or in part.

Discovery export

The capability of exporting compatible metrics for advertising available datasets through the BBMRI Directory was established in M9 as described in D2.02 - Report on the pilot system establishment. The Bigpicture metadata standard is sufficiently rich so as to allow export of compatible metadata for advertising in the BBMRI Directory, as appropriate. The BBMRI Directory is a tool that collects and makes available information about biobanks throughout Europe that are willing to share their data and/or samples, and to collaborate with other research groups. However, Bigpicture is not an official biobank (handling of physical samples indeed being explicitly excluded from the project), and neither are many of its data contributors. There do however exist other external discovery services that could be suitable candidates to fill possible Bigpicture needs for external advertisement, such as for example bio.tools, or other conventional Internet search engines. WP2 will continue discussions with BBMRI Directory, as well as investigate what other opportunities could be appropriate to pursue, in the course of Task 2.6 - Iterative development (M10-M71).

Entitlement management

As per the DoA, Bigpicture will use the REMS Resource Entitlement Management System to manage access requests and granted entitlements to datasets. An overview description of this service is available in D2.02 - Report on the pilot system establishment. The REMS system is intended to provide a unified and automated system where data users will be able to apply for access to hosted datasets, and where data contributors will be able to process requests to datasets under their control. Other platform services will then query REMS for up-to-date entitlements to authorise user access to datasets. This will be possible once the project adopts its upcoming legal framework for data sharing (cf GDPR task force; [Task forces](#) section above), approves the upcoming metadata standard for information on data contributor organisations (cf Metadata task force; [Task forces](#) section above), and decided on acceptable terms of dataset use (cf Metadata task force; [Task forces](#) section above). Until such a time, to enable pilot use for service development purposes, the project uses an interim solution where data contributors communicate directly to the service operating beneficiaries written instruction detailing exactly which individuals (affiliation, name, email) are authorised to access which of their contributed datasets.

The REMS entitlement management workflow is illustrated in Fig. 9-12.

The figure illustrates a user interface for a data access application. On the left, a 'Data user' icon is shown. The main content area displays a browser window with the URL 'bp-rems.sd.csc.fi/application/24'. The browser shows a navigation menu with 'Catalogue', 'Applications', and 'About'. The page title is 'BIGPICTURE' and the main heading is 'Application 2022/14'. A green success message reads 'Application: Success'. Below this, a text block states: 'Fill out and submit the application. Several applicants can be invited as members of the application, and each applicant has to accept the terms of use to gain access.' The application form is titled 'State' and includes a progress bar with stages: 'Apply', 'Approval', and 'Approved'. The 'Apply' stage is active, showing fields for 'Application' (2022/14), 'Title', 'State' (Draft), and 'Latest activity' (2022-10-15 14:24). An 'Events' section at the bottom shows a log entry: '2022-10-15 Joel Hedlund created application 2022/14.'

Fig. 9. A data user who is logged in to REMS using Life Science AAI is filling out a draft application for direct access to a dataset.

When clicking to apply for access to a dataset (for example using a link on a dataset landing page; cf [Landing pages](#) section below) a draft application is created, where the data user can fill in the information required by the data contributor in order to process the data access request. The user experience is illustrated in Fig. 9, which indicates that this example request is indeed in the application stage, which will be followed by an approval stage and hopefully to be concluded in the approved stage, if and when the access request has been approved by the contributor, at which point the dataset will be accessible to the data user through the platform services.

LS LOGIN

Data user

Terms of use

Each member is required to accept the terms of use to access the resources.

[Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International \(CC BY 4.0\)](#)

Accept the terms of use

Base form

Base form for registering a resource

Title of the application (max 100 characters) (optional)

Select type of submission

Actions

Save as draft Send application Delete draft...

Copy as a new application PDF

imi innovative medicines initiative European Union efpia

Fig. 10. A data user uses REMS to indicate acceptance of stated terms of use for the dataset.

Depending on specifics regarding the requirements for sharing the dataset, and circumstances surrounding the data user, "information required" may include signing agreements between Data Contributor and Data User, such as a licence agreement, or a data access agreement if the dataset contains personal data. Fig. 10 shows a simple example where terms of use require no signatures, but simple one-sided acceptance of a standard Creative Commons licence. In practice, exact terms of use are determined by the contributor on a case by case basis for each contributed dataset, however in order to maximise ease of processing access requests, Bigpicture wp3 has developed a set of recommended terms of dataset use (cf Metadata task force; [Task forces](#) section above) with the support of wp5.

Data Access Committee
appointed by
data contributor organisation

Actions

Return to applicant...
Request review ▾
Request decision ▾

Remark...
Approve or reject...
Close application...

Copy as a new application
PDF

Approve or reject

Add comment (shown to applicant)

Comment

+ Upload an attachment
?

Date for access rights to expire (optional)

mm / dd / yyyy

Cancel
Reject
Approve

Every contributed dataset has a designated data access committee (DAC), which is appointed by the data contributor organisation and tasked with processing and approving access requests to that dataset. The data access committee may appoint different DACs for different datasets, or they may choose to appoint the same DAC for all their contributed datasets. Fig. 11 illustrates how the DAC, having been notified of our pending example access request being, has now logged in using Life Science AAI, and is using REMS to review the request. The DAC takes steps necessary to validate the request, and approves or rejects it, optionally with a comment.

Fig. 12. Example notification email sent by REMS to inform the data user that the DAC review of their access request has concluded, with instructions for how to verify the outcome.

The data user is notified of the outcome of the DAC review via email, an example of which is shown in Fig. 12. At this point, the dataset is accessible to the data user through the platform services, if indeed the DAC chose to approve the request.

Data download

As per the DoA, wp2 provides robust backend APIs to enable users to download datasets that they have been granted direct access to; the dataset access request approval process being described in the [Entitlement management](#) section above. The intention is that platform application services such as Cytomine (wp4) will provide frontends for download functionality once support for Life Science AAI authenticated and authorised object storage has been implemented by wp4 as per the DoA. In the meantime, wp2 is providing this functionality through the use of the same sda-cli toolset that is described in the [Data submission](#) section above.

The current process of downloading directly accessible datasets for use in a local research environment begins by requesting a dataset export be generated for download. This request must include the public encryption key that matches the private key that the data user will use to decrypt the downloaded dataset files. This is because -analogously to the scenario described in the [Data submission](#) section above- the exported files will be encrypted prior to transfer. The transfer itself will always occur over an encrypted connection, but the encryption with a recipient-specified key is to ensure that even if the transfer is somehow intercepted by an attacker, the contents of the files will only be readable by the intended recipient of the data. As an extra safeguard, the encrypted export is made available at a hard-to-guess url that is provided only to the requester. The project may decide to develop a dedicated web service for making these requests, should data users or contributors prefer use of the sda-cli toolset over other upcoming frontends such as Cytomine. If so, then this will become possible once the project adopts its upcoming legal framework for data sharing (cf GDPR task force; [Task forces](#) section above), at which time wp2 can take on such development tasks, within available resources and according to project priorities (cf the [Requirement dialogue](#) and [Decision making](#) sections above). Until such a time, to enable pilot use for service development purposes, the project uses an interim solution where data users make such requests directly to the service operating beneficiaries, detailing exactly which

individuals (affiliation, name, email) that the export is intended for, which is matched against the corresponding existing explicit access grants communicated to the service operating beneficiaries in written instruction by the data contributing organisations (as described in the [Entitlement management](#) section) before the export is effected.

When an export has been made, the data user can use sda-cli to download and decrypt the dataset inside their local research environment, as illustrated in Fig. 13.

Similarly, as in use for data submission, the sda-cli frontend for downloads has proven to be quite generically capable, and has been met with uniformly positive feedback from pioneering users of the Bigpicture repository services, and no negative feedback or even feature development requests have arisen. From this, we conclude that the sda-cli toolset is highly suited to meet needs in digital pathology, at least among those highly technologically advanced users at RUMC. However, we do anticipate that the needs for feature development could rise, under the same rationale as described in the [Data submission](#) section above. WP2 will take on such development tasks as needs are identified, within available resources and according to project priorities (cf the [Requirement dialogue](#) and [Decision making](#) sections above).

Services for on-platform data use

As per the DoA, wp2 provides services for on-platform data use. Some, like SD Desktop, are based on services in long-term production operation at the wp2 infrastructure service hosting partners. Others are application services developed by wp4, such as Cytomine, and hosted in the wp2 private execution environment that is provided by the wp2 infrastructure service hosting partners. The current status of these on-platform services is reported in D2.07 - Report on private execution model implementation in operational environment.

Further development

This section describes identified and potential needs for development that have not been described in the sections above.

As described in the above sections in this report, the Bigpicture platform consists of several services which fulfil different needs for project feasibility and platform sustainability. The number of services is

not envisioned to decrease. Rather, the number of services is envisioned to increase, possibly linearly, with each added federated node. Yet, the project has the ambition of providing a user-friendly platform with one 'front door', seamlessly integrating the separate underlying components. As per the DoA, Cytomine is envisioned to provide the frontend user interface to most Bigpicture functionalities, however for the sake of completeness, it is envisioned that there will also exist a Bigpicture service webpage, which will fill the role as 'front door'.

This webpage should link relevant entry points of interest for different usage, namely:

- Datasets
 - Browse [Landing pages](#) website root (existing).
 - Search Federated [Discovery search service](#) interface (existing).
 - Download [Data download](#) request service (if needed).
 - Submit Data submission instructions and entry points (upcoming).
- Algorithms (upcoming, cf below).
 - Browse AI algorithm register / download service.
 - Try Service for indirect access to AI algorithm.
 - Benchmark Service for indirect access to datasets.
 - Submit Algorithm submission entry points.
- Compute
 - Analysis Request [Services for on-platform data use](#) such as [Cytomine](#) (if needed).
 - AI training Guidance on how to procure on-platform GPU HPC resources (if needed).
- Software Link to Cytomine (if needed).
- Metrics Public usage metrics website³ (existing, cf below).

This webpage could be implemented as a static page on the Bigpicture website, or if needed, a small number of static pages. From these starting points, all relevant functionality in Bigpicture platform should be intuitively reachable. Development of this webpage can commence once the project adopts its upcoming legal framework for data sharing (cf GDPR task force; [Task forces](#) section above).

Regarding browsing and submitting algorithms, Bigpicture has not yet started work on an AI algorithm register / download service. The user-facing part of this (e.g. info pages, explanation, using the actual algorithm) will be developed by wp4, whereas the backend container registry services will be provided by wp2, as outlined in D4.05 - Technical description of the application programming interface for integration of AI algorithms in the Bigpicture infrastructure. Ideally, this register should be accessible through Cytomine, so that compatible algorithms can be launched from within Cytomine. Possibly, wp4 could implement this as a "store" in Cytomine, or, alternatively, a static webpage with links to algorithm landing pages on GitHub or similar will suffice.

A potential roadmap toward services for trying and benchmarking algorithms (i.e. indirect access to AI algorithms and datasets) is described in D2.07 - Report on private execution model implementation in operational environment.

Regarding metrics, the only currently reported public metric is the number of bytes stored. However, it is anticipated that the data collector node coordinator board (wp3) will request additional metrics, to better inform of repository composition for example in terms of geography and pathologies. It is also anticipated that wp6 will request that its KPI reports be published on this metrics website. WP2 is ready to implement these additions when needed, within available resources and according to project priorities (cf the [Requirement dialogue](#) and [Decision making](#) sections above).

Regarding further services for on-platform use, as per the DoA, Bigpicture partner Sectra is investigating whether it is possible to provide their pathology image viewer as an on-platform service, for viewing and interacting with images and for making annotations.

³ <https://status.bp.nbis.se/>

We also anticipate that it may be necessary to develop protocols for communicating updates of dataset contents or entitlements to application services that are hosted on the platform, so that appropriate handling of such events can be automated. Having such protocols in place would ensure that events such as access revocations in REMS or dataset updates resulting from GDPR right-to-be-forgotten requests, can be handled timely and consistently by conforming services without requiring manual intervention. In the simplest case, this could take the form of a notification message to inform that a certain dataset has changed, which a conforming service should then react to as necessary, for example by flushing any stale caches, or rebuilding the corresponding entries in any internal databases.

Conclusion

This report provides a description of the state of the operational system at the time when the first real non-clinical data submissions are being prepared and submitted. The platform services were set up as clones of existing production services operated by the wp2 partners to support genetic research. The system was established and operational M10, and has since been iteratively improved by wp2 to suit needs also within pathology, to smaller or greater extent, based on needs identified by the rest of the project, according to project priorities, and within available time and resources. Services have now reached a high degree of technical readiness to open up for wide use, pending project adoption of upcoming legal framework for data sharing and critical metadata standards.

Despite being originally intended for supporting genetics research specifically, the ELIXIR technologies that the Bigpicture repository infrastructure is building upon have proven to be quite generically capable, and have been met with uniformly positive feedback from the digital pathology users of the Bigpicture repository services during the first years of the project. In fact, only very little in terms of negative feedback or even feature development requests have arisen.

From this, we conclude that the platform is highly suited to meet needs in digital pathology, at least among the highly technologically advanced users that have pioneered use of the Bigpicture repository infrastructure services (DECI, MUW, RUMC, RÖ, UMCU). However, as the project moves to more advanced usage patterns and opens up to broader ranges of user organisation which may not have access to the same degree of technological expertise as our pioneers, we do anticipate that the needs for feature development could rise.